

Kuchuktepa is one of the most famous settlements of Uzbekistan

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ANNOTATION: Today, researching archaeological settlements and determining their age is an urgent problem. Therefore, Kuchuktepa settlement was studied through scientific literature.

KEY WORDS: Kuchuktepa, Ancient Bactria, Early Iron Age, Sopollitepa, Pottery. Kuchuktepa was a village fortress of the last Bronze Age and early Iron Age of Southern Uzbekistan. It is located in the Muzrobad micro-oasis, which is part of the Sherabad farming oasis in the direction of Ulaanbuloksay. Its area is 0.5 ha, its height is 8 m. Shaft on top surface. avv. Ceramic pieces belonging to VI-V centuries were collected. In 1963, 1965, 1967, 1977, stratigraphic excavations were made and large-scale archaeological excavations were carried out in Kuchuktepa. Stratigraphic Shurf (shurf N-1) were carried out to the mainland (7.25 cm), and its microstratigraphy was divided into 29 layers. Due to the careful study of the cultural layers of the monument, it was determined that layers 1-18 belong to the Ancient Bactrian (Early Iron) period, and layers 19-29 belong to the Late Bronza period. Also, the analysis of shurf materials in chronological order made it possible to study Kuchuktepa cultural layers into 4 chronological stages (Kuchuk I, Kuchuk II, Kuchuk III, Kuchuk IV).

The ceramic products found there are of particular importance in dividing Kuchuktepa into chronological stages. Chronologically, they included two periods. The lower layers of the monument are ceramic products made by hand without a wheel, fragile, with colorful patterns on the surface, while the upper layer of ceramics consists of high-quality, unpatterned dishes made on a wheel, well-baked

in a two-tiered oven. The vessels made by hand without the aid of a wheel mainly belong to the Kuchuk I period (Late Bronze) and its chronological date is approx. avv. Includes X-VIII centuries.

Colored patterns are placed on the surface of the ceramics along the flange. The patterns are very simple, geometric flowers placed on a pale red angob, i.e., a triangle, a rhombus, and horizontal curves with a dashed inside and a left side. Among the ceramics, up to 20% are vessels made on the potter's wheel. In terms of shape and quality, they do not differ from the ceramics of the Boston phase of the Sopolli culture.

As we mentioned above, during the period of Kuchuk I, ethnic groups of the Chust culture type of Ancient Fergana entered the borders of Bactria. They came to the cities and villages of the Sopolli culture in some places, and in most cases settled in empty places suitable for agriculture, and slowly assimilated into the composition of the local Sopolli culture population, and adopted their unique monumental architectural and cultural traditions.

As a result, a new era begins in the history of South Uzbekistan. This period is called the Ancient Bactrian period in science, and this period has been interpreted as

Kuchuk II, Kuchuk III and Kuchuk IV complexes in the following years. At first, they were interpreted as "Achaemenid era", "Achaemenid ceramics", "Achaemenid culture". Materials from Kuchuktepa proved that the so-called complexes of Ancient Bactrian culture are far from historical truth.

Thus, according to the historical roots of the ancient Bactrian culture, it was determined that it goes back to the Sopolli culture of the Bronze Age. Therefore, the invasion of the successors of the Kuchuk I culture into the territories of Ancient Bactria and the wide spread of monuments of this type throughout the southern regions of Central Asia did not lead to the crisis of the Namazgoh VI and Sopolli cultures, which have been going on for a long time in this land, but on the contrary, it was characteristic of the Ancient Eastern civilization of the native population. economic and cultural traditions continue to develop. The culture of this period is reflected in more than 40 monuments in Southern Uzbekistan, in addition to Kuchuktepa, Kyziltepa, Jondavlattepa, Hayitabadtepa Bandikhontepa, Talashkantepa. It is known from the stratigraphic research conducted in Kuchuktepa that the Kuchuk II stage (from bottom to top) consists of 13-18 layers, its thickness is 1.5 m. avv. It includes the middle of the 8th century and the middle of the 7th century. The main objects of this layer are earthenware made on a wheel, among which there are large bronze paikans with two and three plates. Most of the ceramic vessels consist of cylindrocone-shaped khums and khumchas, and biconical-shaped bowls and bowls.

The collar of khums and khumchas is shaped like a fishing rod, sometimes it is shaped like a horn along the bottom of the bowl. Among the dishes, there are also cone-shaped cups and bowls, and semi-circular dishes. In the lower levels of this layer, fragments of hand-made vessels of the Kuchuk I period were also found.

Layers 9-12 of the stratigraphic layer (thickness of the cultural layer is 1 m.) constitute the Kuchuk III stage of the ancient Bactrian culture. Its periodic date is mil. avv. It is determined by the end of the 7th century and the 6th century. The

characteristic ceramics of this phase consist of cylindroconical, biconical vessels, such as Kuchuk II ceramics. Vessels of this stage are replaced by vessels with small collars. The rims of the bowls are closed and vessels with flat flanges appear, and the ridges below the rims widen and sometimes double, and vessels with slightly turned outwards appear. The last stage of the ancient Bactrian period consists of layers 1-8. Its thickness is 2 m. Period date is mil. avv. It corresponds to the end of the 6th century and the 5th century. The base of the ceramics is wide-collared cylindroconical and biconical vessels. The bowl flange becomes sharp and turns slightly towards the inside of the bowl. The top of the collar becomes oval, and the wavy ridges under the collar characteristic of Kuchuk III stage disappear. At the end of the stage, the flange of the vessel becomes impermeable again, and there are more vessels with wide collars.

Kuchuktepa defense structures and architectural housing complexes were also studied. It is known that in the ceramic complex of the Kuchuk I period, pottery traditions of the Chust culture have been preserved, but in the matter of defense structures and housing construction, the traditions typical of the architecture of the local population continue, that is, at first, 4 m above the mainland in the central part of Kuchuktepa. thick, a platform was built, and defensive structures and housing complexes of the Bronze Age rise above it.

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